

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 06th January 2023

Accepted: 15th January 2023

Online: 17th January 2023

KEY WORDS

Aphorisms, literal translation, semantics, equivalence

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF APHORISMS ABOUT EDUCATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Salayeva Gulrano Zaribbay qizi

Master's degree student of english linguistics department of

Urgench state university solayevagulrano@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7543570>

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the lexical units in English and Uzbek and the problems of their translation. The purpose of the article is to highlight the grammatical and semantic differences between English and Uzbek aphorisms. The source for the article is the opinions of various dictionaries and industry representatives.

INTRODUCTION The attention paid to the language issue in our country, the efforts to raise the prestige and prestige of the state language, the efforts to preserve our native language are important in their essence, and the practical assistance of our enlightened ancestors in realizing their unfulfilled dreams is invaluable. . It is well known that in the process of integration into the world community, it is natural for active language skills to increase as the world market enters. Problems with foreign language teaching are inextricably linked to issues that need to be addressed in mother tongue education. It is no secret that the oral and written literacy of general secondary school graduates has declined. This unfortunate situation creates obstacles for university students in teaching the state language at a high academic level. It is difficult to demand a high level of foreign language proficiency from a student who has not mastered the rules and regulations of their native language. Therefore, improving the quality and effectiveness of mother tongue teaching in secondary school not only serves to maintain the prestige and prestige of the state language, but also provides a basis for students to master the foreign language at the required level. To do this, it is necessary to develop a step-by-step system for assessing the knowledge of the Uzbek language and use modern advanced methods and tools to check the oral and written literacy of graduates, as well as foreign experience in this area.

Analysis and results. An aphorism is a concise, terse, laconic, or memorable expression of a general truth or principle. They are often handed down by tradition from generation to generation. The concept is generally distinct from those of an adage, brocard, chiasmus, epigram, maxim (legal or philosophical), principle, proverb, and saying; although some of these concepts may be construed as types of aphorism. This aphorism was later applied or adapted to physical science and then morphed into multifarious aphorisms of philosophy, morality, and literature. Currently an aphorism is generally understood to be a concise and eloquent statement of truth. Aphorisms are distinct from axioms: aphorisms generally originate from experience and custom, whereas axioms are self-evident truths and therefore require no additional proof. Aphorisms have been especially used in subjects to

which no methodical or scientific treatment was originally applied, such as agriculture, medicine, jurisprudence and politics. Aphoristic collections, sometimes known as wisdom literature, have a prominent place in the canons of several ancient societies, such as the Sutra literature of India, the Biblical Ecclesiastes, Islamic hadiths, the golden verses of Pythagoras, Hesiod's Works and Days, the Delphic maxims, and Epictetus' Handbook. Aphoristic collections also make up an important part of the work of some modern authors. A 1559 oil-on-oak-panel painting, Netherlandish Proverbs (also called The Blue Cloak or The Topsy Turvy World) by Pieter Bruegel the Elder, artfully depicts a land populated with literal renditions of Flemish aphorisms (proverbs) of the day. The first noted published collection of aphorisms is Adagia by Erasmus. Other important early aphorists were Baltasar Gracián, François de La Rochefoucauld and Blaise Pascal. Two influential collections of aphorisms published in the twentieth century were The Uncombed Thoughts by Stanisław Jerzy Lec (in Polish), and Itch of Wisdom by Mikhail Turovsky (in Russian and English).

DISCUSSION Aphorisms are often used to teach a lesson while speaking in plain terms. For example, "A bad penny always turns up" is an aphorism for the fact that bad people or things are bound to turn up in life. We just have to deal with them when they do. This aphorism is motivation. These types of aphorisms lead people to success. And in a word, aphorisms teach us to look at life with confidence. "When cats away the mice will play", we can see from this, the words, "mice" and "cats" refer to people and there is equivalence for it in Uzbek: *"Sulaymon o'ldi devlar qutuldi"*. Besides, we can see another examples: "Time and tide wait for no man" - *Vaqt - g'animat, o'tsa nadomat*. "The least foolish is wise" - *Ahmoqlarga bosh bo'lguncha donolarga yosh bo'l*. These words of wisdom are mainly semantically translated into Uzbek and also the Uzbek equivalents are determined for them. Sometimes, we can come across the aphorisms that are translated literally. Literal translation is a translation of a text done by translating each word separately, without looking at how the words are used together in a phrase or sentence. For instance, "All is one, one is all" - "Hamma bir kishi uchun, bir kishi hamma uchun" Here, "All and One" is generalised, they refer to people. In this table, you can see additional aphorisms which are given with Uzbek equivalents:

ENGLISH	UZBEK
<i>It is never too late to learn</i>	<i>O'rganishning erta-kechi bo'lmaydi</i>
<i>All is one, one is all</i>	<i>Hamma bir kishi uchun, bir kishi hamma uchun</i>
<i>Jack of all trades and master of none</i>	<i>Yuz hunarni chala bilgandan, bir hunarning ustasi bo'lgan yaxshi</i>
<i>No great loss without some small gain</i>	<i>Har bir qiyinchilikning albatta rohati bor</i>
<i>When in doubt, leave out</i>	<i>Ko'zing yetmagan ishga qo'l urma</i>
<i>Go farther and fare worse</i>	<i>Boriga rozi bo'lib, yo'g'iga sabr qilib yashash kerak</i>

Nothing new under the sun

Dunyo ko`rmay, dunyoning kishisi
bo`lolmaysan

Research Methodology. Apart from this , we can see the examples of famous people`s aphorisms about education:

"Learn and read. Read serious books. Life will do the rest." - Fyodor Dostoevsky

"Live as if you will die tomorrow, learn as if you'll live forever" - Mahatma Gandhi

"Many people want to know, to strive for knowledge - not all of them."

"We are learning all his life, apart from a dozen years spent in school"-Gabriel Laub.

CONCLUSION

In the process of analysis it can be concluded that English aphorisms are translated from a semantic point of view. Through the analysis of aphorisms in English and Uzbek, the Uzbek language can develop linguistic culture. Many aphorisms were created in ancient times and still with the people who are their creators. Aphorisms are popular, passed down from generation to generation and live for centuries.

A seach nation has its own way of thinking, it also affects their wisdom. Even though the themes in the aphorisms are similar, the images in them are unique.

The Uzbek people are justifiably proud of their contribution to the world's spiritual treasury. Wisdom is a priceless gift from wise ancestors to future generations.

References:

1. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aphorism#cite_ref-1
2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/comparative-linguistic-analysis-of-uzbek-and-english-aphorisms>
3. <https://kpi.ua/en/aphorism-education%20>
4. <https://www.uwed.uz/uz/news/fulltext/1616>
5. Cambridge advanced learner`s dictionary 4th edition
6. Kimsanova G. " Comparative analysis of English proverbs and sayings expressing senility and youth" .
7. <https://maqollar.uz/page/12>
8. Radin. P "A study in American English Mythology" New York 1992.
9. J. Raymond. 1956. Tensions in Proverbs: More Light on International Understanding. Western Folklore 15.3, pg 153-154